

STATISTICAL MODELLING OF RESIDENTS' CONCERNS TOWARDS SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT FACILITY: A CASE STUDY OF THREE TOWNS IN SOUTHEASTERN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to investigate the general attitude and concerns of residents of three cities in Southeastern Nigeria towards the present waste management practices, the siting of an SWM facility and the residents' likely attitude towards such facility. A questionnaire was designed and administered in three cities: Aba, Umuahia, and Owerri in southeastern Nigeria. The questions assessed residents' general attitude and concerns of the impact of present waste management practices, and the siting of a new solid waste management (SWM) facility. Using factor analysis by principal component method, four components were extracted namely; "pollution and health effects (F1)", "nuisance (F2)", "damage to the nature (F3)" and "general attitude towards construction of waste management facilities (F4)". However, F1, F2, and F3 were found to be statistically significant when modeled with concern variable. Comparison of concerns using the means of the factors indicated that the cities were more concerned over the "pollution and health effect" of waste management (mean of concern, 2.70 on a 3.0 scale), followed by "nuisance" (2.20) and then "damage to nature" (2.11). Rating of concerns was different in the three cities reflecting perceptions, attitude, and possible behavior towards waste management. Overall, concerns in Umuahia and Owerri (capital cities) were approximately 11% and 16% higher than in Aba, a commercial and fast industrializing city respectively. Issues in improving waste management in Nigeria were also discussed.

KEYWORDS: waste management, concern, attitude, behavior, factor analysis, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Solid waste management (SWM) has been an integral part of every human society (Shekdar, 2009). This problem has been increasing with change in consumption pattern, - increase in consumerism and unavailability of waste management facilities. It is obvious that different communities have different unique profile of solid waste, the composition of which depends on variables such as urbanization. Lack of sound policies for waste management by the government, inadequate infrastructure, and the unwillingness of people to co-operate and participate in waste management activities are major challenges facing sustainable waste management in developing countries. One obvious consequence of rapid urbanization is the growing generation of solid wastes and many city authorities face unprecedented challenges in managing these, including problems of coping with their collection and disposal (Li'ao *et al*, 2009; Longe and Williams, 2006). Presently, the developed countries are faced with improving on existing waste management facilities to meet higher environmental quality criteria, whereas the developing countries are struggling with providing the basic waste collection and disposal facilities to meet with the command-and-control burn-or-bury strategy. In most developing and transitional countries, solid wastes are handled using inappropriate means by poorly educated workers. The result is loss of recoverable resources and environmental pollution.

To increase people's acceptance level of an SWM facility, dialogue with neighbors and public involvement in the planning stage are necessary. Minn *et al.* (2010), documented that raising public awareness is important but simply creating awareness is not enough to promote the peoples' participation in SWM. The participatory management approach cannot be achieved if the municipality fails to share critical decision-making power with the people and fails to facilitate the participation process. For better communication

with citizens, it is essential to understand people's concerns and concepts of SWM management facilities. This is also essential for better solid waste management practice.

Any effort at achieving a sustainable resource and waste management practice will also demand a more responsible behavior by producers and consumers (Nnorom *et al.*, 2009).

In most developing countries, waste materials including potentially hazardous wastes and recyclables are disposed at open dumps (Taghipoura and Mosafarib, 2009; Longe and Williams, 2006; Osibanjo and Nnorom, 2007). These inappropriate waste management techniques have resulted in serious concerns and environmental pollution. Deteriorating environmental conditions may be a factor in determining residents' willingness to participate in appropriate waste management practices (Nnorom *et al.*, 2009). For an SWM facility to be accepted, it should be environmental friendly, economically sound, and socially acceptable. An SWM facility that is not accepted may be opposed by residents (Furuichi, 1999). Social movements and conflicts between residents and an authority sometimes lead to closure of a facility.

Literature abound on studies conducted at the regional and global level with the aim of finding solutions to solid waste management especially with the aggravation of this problem by urbanization and population growth (Kuniyal *et al.*, 1998; Suttibak and Nitivattananon, 2008; De Feo and Malvano, 2009). Improper waste management can lead to environmental pollution, unpleasant smells, foster the growth and multiplication of insects, rodents, and worms, and may lead to transmission of diseases like typhoid, cholera, and malaria. Population growth contributes to solid waste production (Li'ao *et al.*, 2009). The estimated annual growth rate of MSW is 3.2-4.5% in developed countries, 2-3% in developing countries, and 8-10% in China (Li'ao *et al.*, 2009). In fact, it is estimated that China produces 29% of the world's MSW each year (Hui *et al.*, 2006).

Waste management practices in Nigeria are far from being sustainable. Wastes are separated neither at source nor at the collection points. The collection points (open dumps) are usually located within residential suburbs. Such dumps are usually set afire to reduce waste volume before being carted away in truck to dug-up pits for burial. Improper waste management also increases greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, which contribute to climate change. Hence, improved waste management in developing countries is necessary in combating climate change.

Most cities in Nigeria are faced with the problems of population increase, rapid expansion, and urbanization. Also of concern is the increase in industrial activities without consideration of best available technologies and abatement equipments. These have no doubt, brought increasing strain on the existing inadequate urban infrastructure. This strain appears to be more obvious in waste management where the existing system, which still adopts the old 'collect and bury' system, appears to be incapable of coping with the mountain load of waste generated and heaped on the surface within neighborhoods. Wastes generated and disposed at open dumps include virtually all categories of solid waste: food wastes, paper, cardboard, plastics, textiles, leather, yard wastes, wood, glass, metals, ashes, potentially hazardous wastes including consumer electronics, medical/hospital waste, batteries (dry cells, and rechargeable batteries) condemned oil, waste tires etc (Nnorom and Osibanjo, 2006; Ekhaise and Omavwoya, 2008; Oyelola and Babatunde, 2008).

Cao *et al.*, (2009) observed that environmental attitudes and values have shifted significantly towards an increased concern for the environment in recent decades. The knowledge of the sources and types of waste in an area, as well as the attitude of the waste generators are required in order to design and operate appropriate solid waste management systems. Attitude and concerns have been critical issues in waste management.

Zeiss, (1991) proposed consecutive linkage starting from physical impacts to beliefs, and finally to attitudes. He classified impacts into two categories: physical and non-physical. Physical impacts include

health risks, nuisances, and environmental change and these in turn generate non-physical impacts, which are categorized into economic (example, property value decrease) and social (community image loss) impacts. Fear about physical impact are usually exaggerated by residents and do not correspond to actual damage, and non-physical impacts affect attitudes as strongly as physical ones. Therefore, a minor physical impact may trigger a very strong negative attitude to an SWM facility.

In terms of physical impact, pollution causes psychological stress and fear of health risks (Petts and Eduljee, 1994; Becker, 2001). The perception of risk is a factor in changing attitudes, and a risk is considered greater when the hazard is involuntary and uncontrollable, not natural and cannot be compensated for by any benefits (Petts, 1994).

Citizen's attitudes depend on knowledge about a facility among others. In addition, residents tend to show more negative attitudes to unfamiliar facilities of which they have no experience compared with similar facilities that already exist (Zeiss, 1991).

Citizens concerns relevant to acceptance or attitude to an SWM facility as obtained in literature are summarized in Table 1. Since there was a great diversity of terminology in literature, similar words and expression were integrated and gathered under the same group. Among physical impacts, pollution and its health effect was undoubtedly one of the most important. Air, surface water, groundwater, and soil are major polluted media, and there are various pollutants. Influence on the environment is also considered, including effect on wildlife, forest destruction, and land conversion.

Physical impact creates a nuisance, which is more of an emotional effect than actual pollution. The physical impacts take various forms: odor, litter, and pest such as flies and rodents. Non-physical impacts, such as impairment of landscape or views by an SWM facility and a decrease in property value can be categorized in the nuisance group. The factors influencing personal judgment and acceptance of SWM facilities are grouped under personal factors which include (1) environmental awareness and (2) risk perception.

Rahardyan *et al.* (2004) investigated residents' concern about SWM facilities in Japan and their attitudes towards such facilities using three municipalities. Of the many concerns, "pollution and health effects" had the highest rating followed by "reliability of the SWM facility", "damage to the nature" and "cost of the SWM facility". Also the ratings were different between the municipalities, reflecting their geographic and social backgrounds.

The objective of this study was to investigate peoples' concerns about a hypothetical SWM facility and make clear which concerns are the most influential to attitudes towards constructing and operating such facilities within their neighborhood. For this purpose, firstly, key variables or concerns were extracted by literature review, and then a questionnaire structure was designed. Secondly, priorities among concerns and their inter-relations were identified. Thirdly, the relationship between identified concerns and attitudes towards SWM facilities were analyzed.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

For the purpose of the study, a well-structured questionnaire was designed. The first part of the questionnaire was questions to ascertain the degree of concern on various aspects of SWM, while the second part inquires about attitudes. In the later section concerns in the first and second parts were compared with attitudes, so these are referred to as "concern variable" or just "variables" in the subsequent sections. Each question was identified with a number from question one to question thirteen. Before answering, each respondent was asked to imagine that an SWM facility is been constructed in his/her neighborhood. The type of facility was however not specified.

The first part (Questions 1–10) included questions to discover the extent of the respondent's concerns about impact or damage caused by an SWM facility. This part had two sub-groups of question. The first is termed

“pollution and health effect” question. A typical question under this subsection assessed the respondent’s perception of “damage to environment” from the prevailing waste management practices. This damage was aggregated into damage to “plant & animal”, and damage to “forest resources”. These concern issues were rated into four scales; “very worried”, “worried”, “slightly worried” and “not worried at all”. A “Not sure (NS)” option was also provided.

In the second part (Questions 11-13) questions regarding attitudes toward solid waste treatment facilities were investigated. A typical question assessed the respondent’s attitude assuming an SWM facility is cited or being cited within 1km from the respondent’s residence. Respondent’s attitude was rated as either “in favor”, “not concerned” or “opposed”. This section of the questionnaire also investigated respondents concerns about recycling activities, and their willingness to participate in efforts at achieving sustainable waste management in the country. A summary of the structure of the questionnaire is given in Table 1.

Surveyed Cities

The questionnaire was administered to residents of three cities in southeastern Nigeria: Aba, Umuahia, and Owerri within the period of January through April, 2009. Aba is a city in Abia state located along the Aba River. The city of Aba has a current population estimate of approximately 1 million. It once served as an administrative center of Britain’s colonial government but today is a fast industrializing city as well as a major commercial center. The city has always had problem with waste management despite effort by the various governments to clean-up the town. Owerri is the capital of Imo State with a current population of about 301,873 (NPC, 2006) and is approximately 40 square miles in area. Owerri is an administrative town with greater percentage of her population made up of civil servants and traders. The city is also facing waste disposal challenges. Umuahia is the capital of Abia State also in southeastern Nigeria. Umuahia has a current population estimate of 359,230 (NPC, 2006). It has few industries mainly agro-industries and today is an administrative town with an increasing problem of waste management.

The key population indices of the two states studied is given in Table 2. Abia state with a total population of 2.83 million (2.0% of the total Nigerian population) with a population density (persons per sq km) of 578 and percentage urban population of 5.74%. Imo state with a total population of 3.93 million (2.8% of the total Nigerian population) has a population density (persons per sq km) of 744 and percentage urban population of 32.64%.

DATA ANALYSIS /RESULTS

Factor analysis was used to uncover the latent structure of concern variables in the responses. Three hundred questionnaires were administered in each of the towns surveyed. After excluding incompletely filled questionnaires, and other questionnaires with ‘not sure’ answer, data from 607 respondents (196 from Aba, 202 from Umuahia and 209 from Owerri) were used for the factor analysis. The eigen values for each of the factors are shown in Table 3. Using the Guttman-Kaiser rule (Field, 2000) which suggests that only those factors with an eigen value larger than 1 should be retained, it is clear from Table 3 that four factors have eigen values greater than one. Thus, Four (4) principal components (or factors) were extracted by the principal component method with varimax rotation. Component loading are shown in Table 4. Loadings above 0.6 are usually considered ‘high’ and those below 0.4 are ‘low’ (Garson, 1998). In Table 4, 0.5 was used as a criterion, and variables are arranged in the order of component loadings in each factor. From Table 4 the following factors were extracted [see Table 5 for the extracted factors];

The first component comprised Q1 and Q2 and is termed ‘pollution and health effect (F1)’.

The second component, comprised Q3, Q4 and Q5 is termed ‘damage to nature (F2)’.

The third component is termed ‘nuisance (F3)’ and it included Q6, Q7, Q8, Q9 and Q10.

The fourth component is termed the ‘general attitude towards the construction of a waste management facility (F4)’ and it included Q11, Q12, and Q13.

Modeling Concern

Here respondents selected their level of concern from four alternatives;

- (i) Not concerned at all (yes = 1)
- (ii) Not very much concerned (yes = 2)
- (iii) Somewhat concerned (yes = 3)
- (iv) Very much concerned (yes = 4)

The survey results for the concern variable are given in table 7. From table 7, it can be seen that 38.9% of the respondents are either not concerned at all or not very much concerned while 61.1% are somewhat or very much concerned about the impact of sitting a new SWM facility in their neighbourhood.

When response variable is ordinal and has more than two levels, Analysts have a choice of ordered logit and ordered probit models. Considering that the ordered probit is theoretically superior to most other models, it would be applied to the data analyzed in this study. Stata (Statacorp, LD, College Station, Texas) was used to estimate ordered probit model that explained the relationship between the level of concern and the extracted factors (Table 8). From the results of Table 8, it is clear that out of the four factors (F1, F2, F3 and F4), three of them (F1, F2, and F3) are statistically significant.

Concerns about SWM facilities

Comparison of Concerns

The extracted concerns were compared among the three surveyed cities. For each question, the answer was rated with '3' to '0' scores: for example "very worried" was rated as '3' and 'not worried at all' was '0'. 'Not sure' and no answer were excluded in the calculation. In each sub-group of concerns, concerned items were arranged in order of an overall average score (Table 6).

From the comparison of the three significant factors, 'pollution and health effect' had the highest rating (with an average score of 2.70), followed by 'nuisance' (with 2.20 average score), and then 'damage to nature' (with an average score of 2.11). This implies that respondents' concern ranged over various aspects and was not limited to a specific object. Under 'pollution and health effect', 'air pollution' had a higher rating than 'water pollution'. The belief within the population that one can live with treated water (Sachet, boiled and bottled water) may explain the low concern for water pollution.

When score were compared among towns, Umuahia had highest ratings with respect to 'air pollution'. Overall Umuahia and Owerri had higher ratings than Aba, which seems to reflect that Aba has low environmental pressures or do not see the environment as a serious issue.

DISCUSSION

Considering that the sitting and construction of a new SWM facility is a big challenge in Nigeria in view of the fact majority are concerned about the impact of such facility, an SWM should be socially accepted as well as environmentally and economically sound. An SWM facility that is not acceptable by the residents may lead to its closure as a result of the unwillingness of the residents to cooperate and participate in the usefulness of such a facility. In view of this, the results of this study are quite interesting, in that, it extracted the major concerns of the residents in southeastern Nigeria towards the siting of an SWM facility within their neighborhoods. The significant concerns as extracted from the study in order of priority are;

- (i) Concern for pollution and health effects; some of the chemicals used in the treatment of waste may result in land pollution. As a result of burning some of the waste in an incinerator, gaseous substances that are dangerous to health may pollute the air.
- (ii) Nuisance; consistent noise resulting from the operating machines of the facility or the delivery vehicles, decrease of property value, odor, dust and litter and vibrations are also of concern to the residents

- (iii) Damage to the nature; influence on flora and fauna/ wild life and conversion of the environment were also of significant concern

There is no question that an SWM facility would be accepted by the residents if their main concerns as extracted from this study were considered and would be addressed at least to a reasonable extent by the constructing agents and facility being constructed.

It was also discovered that ratings of concerns were different among the surveyed cities (Table 6) which may be as a result the varying backgrounds. This reflects the perception, attitude, and possible behavior of the residents towards waste in the cities surveyed. Ratings were generally higher in Umuahia and Owerri, which are capital cities and therefore administrative towns with greater percentage of the population being literate. Aba, a commercial and fast industrializing city showed the lowest value for most items, which seems to reflect low interest on waste management.

Using factor analysis, four principal components/factors were extracted of which three of them were found to be statistically significant. They were named “Nuisance”, “Pollution and effect”, and “damage to nature”. Comparison of concerns using the means of the factors indicated that the cities were more concerned over the “pollution and health effect” of waste management (mean of concern, 2.70 on a 3.0 scale), followed by “nuisance” (2.20) and then “damage to nature” (2.11). Rating of concerns was different in the three cities reflecting perceptions, attitude, and possible behavior towards waste management. Overall, concerns in Umuahia (2.31) and Owerri (2.42) (capital cities) were approximately 11% and 16% higher than in Aba (2.09), a commercial and fast industrializing city respectively.

The results of this study are similar to the results of Rehardyan *et al.* (2004), in the sense that “pollution and health effects” has the highest rating among the five principal components extracted. It is also similar to it in that ratings were different among the surveyed municipalities. This study is also in support of Furuichi (1999) that an SWM facility that is not accepted may be opposed by the residents. And for the residents to accept an SWM facility, their major concerns must be addressed.

In recent years, there has been a paradigm shift in urban infrastructure development and management from a dominance of the public sector to an emphasis on private sector provision of services (Ogu, 2000). This should be taken into consideration in policy development and implementation in solid waste management in the developing countries.

Air pollution was of great concern to our respondents, therefore great measures should be adopted in addressing air pollution. This stems from the present waste management practice in which waste is burned openly within inhabited areas with the stench and smoke constituting nuisance to residents. Raising awareness among the waste generators, the collectors, and recyclers/ disposal agents of the potential dangers of inappropriate disposal and management of un-sorted municipal waste can contribute to building new attitudes toward effective management of MSW.

To achieve effective management of MSW in Nigeria, the following issues require urgent attention:

- learning from the experience and know-how of existing waste collection and management models abroad,
- providing basic and environmentally sound waste management facilities (including waste-to-energy facilities)
- educating stakeholders (generators, handlers etc) on the new system of waste policy, and; most importantly,
- encouraging stakeholders to successfully transiting from the current waste management practice

However, studies have observed that the efficacy of the implementation of a policy by government depends mainly on the attitude that government shows citizens towards these problems, but also on the measures

implemented under the government's plan (Cao *et al*, 2009; Junquera *et al*, 2001). Therefore, it is imperative that the government policy be consistent with effective implementation. It is important to educate and mobilize society to segregate recyclables for the effective and sustainable management of solid wastes.

The key strategies in achieving effective waste management in Nigeria includes awareness campaign and waste education; effective monitoring of industrial activities; encouraging waste separation at source/collection points, and the introduction of stringent legislation/regulations and guidelines on waste management

CONCLUSION

In the construction of any SWM Facility, a comprehensive study of concerns and attitude should be employed. Considering that different cities with different background tend to have varying degrees of concerns for different variables. The citizens should always be a key factor during the planning stages, and should be involved throughout the stages of the project: conception, planning, construction, and operation. This way the community will not be a problem to the facility and would rather perceive such a facility as a means of protecting the environment.

In this study, people's concerns towards SWM facilities and their relation with attitudes to SWM facilities were analyzed. This survey indicated that the highest concern of the population surveyed was "Pollution and health effect", followed by "Nuisance", and "damage to nature" in that order. This means that people's concern ranged over various aspects and was not limited to a specific item under the concerns outlined. Under the category, "pollution and health effect" "Air pollution" showed the higher level of concern. There is therefore a need to review the present waste management policy in the country.

It is imperative to adopt the three 'R' strategies as a national policy in waste management in Nigeria. In achieving this, public education and involvement are crucial, and in the case of reduction, they are imperative. Reduction assumes the commitment and involvement of all citizens. Source reduction strategies have many favorable environmental impacts, including reducing greenhouse gas production, saving energy, and conserving resources, in addition to reducing the volume of the waste stream. Achieving the desired goals of effective and sustainable waste management in Nigeria requires policy/guideline formulation, provision of waste management facilities, and implementing an effective waste education to enable stakeholders' transit from the present to the desired strategy. Information on sustainable consumption patterns should also be integrated into the education system. Regulation and legislation are instrumental to changes in waste management practice. This therefore should be a key strategy in improving on waste management practices in the developing countries.

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Table 1: Structure of questionnaire used in the study

Suppose a Waste Management Disposal facility (Incinerator Facility, Landfill or Material Recovery Facility is Planned to be Constructed in the Town where you are, Concerning each item below, Please select a relevant choice

For example the atmosphere is polluted by emission from a facility

Question - How much are you worried about....?.

Q(1) Air pollution

1. Very worried 2. Worried 3. Slightly worried 4. Not worried at all 5. Not sure

Q(2) Water pollution

1. Very worried 2. Worried 3. Slightly worried 4. Not worried at all 5. Not sure

Q(3) Degradation of Soil fertility

1. Very worried 2. Worried 3. Slightly worried 4. Not worried at all 5. Not sure

Q(4) Plants and animals

1. Very worried 2. Worried 3. Slightly worried 4. Not worried at all 5. Not sure

Q(5) Forest

1. Very worried 2. Worried 3. Slightly worried 4. Not worried at all 5. Not sure

Q(6) Stench and noise of facility

1. Very worried 2. Worried 3. Slightly worried 4. Not worried at all 5. Not sure

Q(7) Flies and rodents

Q(8) Deterioration of living environment

1. Very worried 2. Worried 3. Slightly worried 4. Not worried at all 5. Not sure

Q(9) Decrease of property value

1. Very worried 2. Worried 3. Slightly worried 4. Not worried at all 5. Not sure

Q(10) Influence on farm products_

1. Very worried 2. Worried 3. Slightly worried 4. Not worried at all 5. Not sure

Q(11) If a Landfill is constructed in the area about 1 Km from your house, do you agree or oppose it

1. In favor 2. Not concerned 3. Opposed 4. Not sure

Q(12) If an Recycling facility is constructed in the area about 1 Km from your house, do you agree or oppose it –

1. In favor 2. Not concerned 3. Opposed 4. Not sure

Q(13) How much do you dislike waste

1. Disliked very much 2. Disliked 3. Not so disliked 4. Not disliked at all 5. Not sure

General concern

Q (14) Generally if an SWM facility is be constructed in your neighborhoods, how much concerned are you?

1. Not concerned at all 2. Not very much concerned 3. Concerned 4. Very much concerned

Table 2: Data on Population and GDP of the Surveyed Municipalities

State	total population	percent of population	population density (persons per sq km)	percent urban population	GDP per capita (Naira)
Abia	2833999	2.0	578	5.74	1565
Imo	3934899	2.8	744	32.64	956
Nigeria	140,004,542	100	304	36.3	1154

Adapted from Madu (2009)

Table 3: Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigen values			Rotation sums of squared loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.696	28.428	28.428	2.868	22.065	22.065
2	3.041	23.389	51.817	2.523	19.408	41.473
3	2.058	15.832	67.649	2.517	19.364	60.838
4	1.024	7.874	75.523	1.909	14.686	75.523
5	0.792	6.095	81.000			
6	0.683	5.253	86.872			
7	0.578	4.446	91.318			
8	0.334	2.571	93.889			
9	0.267	2.055	95.944			
10	0.204	1.567	97.511			
11	0.159	1.227	98.738			
12	0.119	0.917	99.655			
13	4.485 x 10 ²	0.345	100.000			

Extraction method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization

Table 4: Sorted rotated factor loadings and communality.

Variables	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4	Communality
Q12	0.898	0.117	-0.011	0.155	0.844
Q13	0.868	-0.091	-0.163	0.203	0.829
Q11	0.846	0.008	0.240	0.080	0.780
Q9	0.541	0.122	0.402	0.321	0.573
Q6	-0.044	0.916	-0.110	-0.037	0.855
Q7	0.122	0.890	-0.077	0.099	0.822
Q8	-0.045	0.683	-0.284	-0.285	0.630
Q10	0.457	0.505	-0.078	-0.0335	0.383
Q1	0.038	0.164	-0.928	-0.040	0.890
Q2	0.084	0.175	-0.921	-0.213	0.907
Q5	-0.119	0.244	-0.010	-0.859	0.811
Q4	-0.080	-0.193	-0.492	-0.693	0.766
Q3	-0.210	0.066	-0.464	-0.515	0.529

Table 5 Factors related to citizen’s acceptance of SWM facilities

Sub-group	Factor	Examples
Factor 1	Pollution and its health effects.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fear of pollution occurrence • Fear of risk
Factor 2	Damage to environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Influence on flora and fauna/wild life • Conversion of the environment.
Factor 3	Nuisance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Odor, dust and litter • Insects and pests. • Impairment of landscape and view.
Factor 4	Attitude towards facility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decrease of property value. • Community facility • Employment

Table 6. Comparison of concerns

Question	Aba	Owerri	Umuahia	Mean	Average of Mean Scores
Q ₁	2.63	2.77	2.80	2.73	2.70
Q ₂	2.47	2.73	2.80	2.67	
Q ₃	1.90	2.27	2.53	2.23	2.11
Q ₄	1.80	2.43	2.27	2.17	
Q ₅	1.57	2.30	1.97	1.95	
Q ₆	2.30	2.13	2.13	2.19	2.20
Q ₇	2.23	2.33	2.27	2.27	
Q ₈	2.03	2.27	2.30	2.20	
Q ₉	1.67	2.53	1.90	2.03	
Q ₁₀	2.30	2.43	2.13	2.29	
Average	2.09	2.42	2.31		

Table 7: General Concern towards the Construction of a New SWM Facility

Concern variable	Frequency	%
1. Not concerned at all	106	17.5
2. Not very much concerned	130	21.4
3. Somewhat concerned	162	26.7
4. Very much concerned	209	34.4
Total	607	100.0

Table 8: Model estimation Results for the Concern Variable

Variable	Coefficient	Robust Standard Error
Pollution and health effects (F1)	-0.6417**	0.0258
Damage to the nature (F2)	0.9730**	0.4073
Nuisance (F3)	0.1193*	0.0813
General attitude towards the Construction an SWM facility (F4)	-0.0212	0.0179
τ_1	-0.5481	0.1961
τ_1	0.1324	0.1892
τ_1	0.7483	0.2160

Notes; Number of observations = 607; OP results; log-likelihood = -812. 1240; p-value = 0.0001; “**” and “***” are significant at 5% and 1% level of significance; $\tau_{i's}$ are thresholds estimated along with the parameters of the model.

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